

Studies on Indigoid Dyes. Part X. Benzylidene-2-(4-iodo) 3-oxy 2, 3 dihydrothionaphthenes

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Preparation of *m*-iodophenylthioglycollic acid and 4-iodothioindoxyl is reported.

Ten new iodothioindogenides have been prepared by the condensation of 4-iodothioindoxyl successively with benzaldehyde and its derivatives, cinnamaldehyde and eight more by condensing 6-iodothioindoxyl and 7-iodothioindoxyl respectively with *p*-methoxy, *o*-hydroxy, 3-methoxy-4-hydroxy-, benzaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde.

Dyeing and other properties of the iodothioindogenides have been studied and compared with those of the isomeric 5-iodo-, 6-iodo- and 7-iodothioindogenides.

In the present investigation the influence of an iodine atom in every available position namely, 4-, 5-, 6-, and 7- of the thionaphthene part of the thioindogenide molecules on the depth of the colour has been studied.

4-Iodothioindoxyl was obtained by the cyclisation of *m*-iodophenylthioglycollic acid, which in turn was prepared from *m*-iodoaniline in the usual way¹. Ten new iodothioindogenides (N₁-N₁₀) have been prepared by condensing 4-iodothioindoxyl successively with benzaldehyde, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes, *p*-dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylamino-benzaldehydes, *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde, *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde.

6-Iodothioindoxyl and 7-iodothioindoxyl have been successively condensed with *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde, *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde affording the dyes (N₁₁-N₁₈).

These compounds have the general formula (N) : (See next page)

The preparation of these iodothioindogenides have been effected by the condensation of equimolecular quantities of the constituents in absolute ethanol in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid.

The iodothioindogenides obtained from benzaldehyde and its derivatives are generally yellow to brown in colour except when the products are derived from *p*-dimethyl- and *p*-diethyl aminobenzaldehydes (red). The solution of the iodothioindogenide in concentrated sulphuric acid produces characteristic colouration and the original compounds are reprecipitated unchanged on treatment with water. The compounds of this series are difficult to reduce by alkaline hydrosulphite and a much lighter shade is produced on cotton.

The absorption maxima of these compounds were determined in pyridine solution with the help of a Hilger and Watts' spectrophotometer and these together with logarithm molar extinction co-efficients are shown in Table 1.

(N₁-N₉, N₁₁-N₁₃, N₁₅-N₁₇)

(N₁₀, N₁₄, N₁₈)

For the sake of comparison, the previously reported absorption maxima of the 5-², 6-³ and 7-³ iodo series are collated.

The maxima of the thioindogenides of the 4-iodo series when arranged give the following order :

It will be seen from the Table 1 that the absorption maxima of the compounds of the four different series are of the order :

A scrutiny of the above results show :

- (a) In all the four iodo series the different groups have the same order of absorption maxima except when—
 - (i) in the 5-iodo series, 4'-NO₂ and 2'-OH derivatives show the same maxima, and
 - (ii) in the 4-iodo series, 4'-NO₂ and 2'-OH derivatives have the maxima in opposite order compared to 6-iodo and 7-iodo series.
- (b) The 2'-NO₂ derivatives in all the four series records a lower maximum than the parent dye and in fact shows the lowest maximum.

TABLE 1

T = 3 Oxy 2,3-dihydrothionaphthene

Compound	Py max, m μ	log ϵ	Ref. No.
Benzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	448	4.169	2
Benzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	438	4.126	
Benzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	437	4.139	3
Benzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	436	4.114	3
2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	447	3.913	2
2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	437	3.875	
2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	434	3.876	3
2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	432	4.040	3
3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	449	3.979	2
3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	439	4.059	
3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	438	4.006	3
3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	437	3.903	3
4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	462	3.798	2
4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	456	4.156	
4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	450	4.115	3
4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	449	4.191	3
4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	506	4.585	2
4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	499	4.633	
4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	498	4.677	3
4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	495	4.611	3
4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T	514	3.866	2
4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	509	4.676	
4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	507	4.666	3
4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	506	4.532	3
4'Methoxybenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T ⁴	455	4.306	
4'Methoxybenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	448.5	4.343	
4'Methoxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	448	4.333	
4'Methoxybenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	446	4.382	
2'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T ⁴	462	5.777	
2'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	453	4.291	
2'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	452	4.197	
2'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	450	4.236	
3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)T ⁴	466	4.409	
3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	460	4.376	
3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	458	4.440	
3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	456	4.466	
Cinnamylidene-2-(5-iodo)T ⁴	470	3.268	
Cinnamylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	464	3.678	
Cinnamylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	462	3.651	
Cinnamylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	461	4.233	

In this series of iodothioindogenides, the iodo substituent at the 5-position of the thionaphthene and an electron donating substituent at the 4-position of the benzaldehyde produce the most pronounced exaltation in the absorption maxima of the compounds.

The 2'-NO₂ derivatives in all the four halo series of 2-iodothionaphthene benzylidenes record a lower maxima than the parent dye and in fact shows the lowest maximum. The reason for this is obviously due to steric crowding and deviation from planarity. Nitro group at *meta* position to the carbon linking the benzene ring to the thioindoxyl ring, produces very little change from the unsubstituted benzene compound, while nitro at the *para* position produces a distinct increase in wavelength of absorption. Combining the benzene ring with an additional -CH = CH- produces only a moderate enhancement in the wavelength of absorption as compared to the electron donating groups like -N(CH₃)₂ and -N(C₂H₅)₂ at the *para* position of the benzylidene attached to the thioindoxyl.

The logarithm molar extinction co-efficient (log ϵ) of the iodothioindogenides shown in Table 1 are around 4, and the order of 4-iodo series are given below :

4'-N(C₂H₅)₂ > 4'-N(CH₃)₂ > 3'-OCH₃-4'-OH > 4'-OCH₃ > 2'-OH > 4'-NO₂ > unsubstituted > 3'-NO₂ > 2'-NO₂ > -CH = CH-.

In the 4-iodo, 5-iodo and 7-iodo series the -CH = CH- group shows the lowest intensity (3.678, 3.268 and 3.651) whereas in the 6-iodo series it is the 3'-NO₂ group (3.903). These results also show that the unsubstituted benzene undergoes $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition with moderate ease compared to all the differently substituted thioindogenides studied in any particular halo series.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of m-iodophenylthioglycollic acid : A solution of sodium nitrite (8.4 g.) in water (15 ml.) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of *m*-iodoaniline (21.9 g.) in concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 ml.) and water (90 ml.) at 0°-2°. The diazo solution was added to a solution of potassium xanthate (24 g.), anhydrous sodium carbonate (48 g.) and water (200 ml.) kept on a water-bath. The mixture was chilled and then extracted with ether. The brown oily liquid obtained after the removal of ether was refluxed for 1 hr. with a mixture of sodium hydroxide (21.5 g.), water (43 ml.) and ethanol (135 ml.).

A solution of monochloroacetic acid (18.8 g.) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (10%, 8.5 ml.) was added and the boiling continued for another hour. Ethanol was removed by distillation and the required acid was precipitated in cold with strong hydrochloric acid. The acid was recrystallised from boiling water (bone charcoal) in pale yellow shining flakes, m.p. 62°-63°, yield 80%. (Found : C, 32.52; H, 2.41. C₈H₇O₂IS requires C, 32.66; H, 2.38%).

4-Iodothioindoxyl : *m*-Iodophenylthioglycollic acid (5 g.) dissolved in chlorobenzene (30 ml.) was heated at 70° with phosphorous trichloride (6 ml.) and stirred continuously for 30 mins. The temperature was brought down to 20° and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (10 g.) was added in small quantities at a time. The mixture was cooled and poured over ice (50 g.). Chlorobenzene was removed by steam distillation. On further

distillation with superheated steam and on cooling the distillate, 4-iodothioindoxyl separated, which was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°), m.p. 120°–21°, yield 45%. (Found : C, 35.01; H, 1.96, C₈H₅OIS requires C, 34.78; H, 1.81%).

Benzylidene (or nitrobenzylidene)-2-(4-iodo) 3 oxy 2,3-dihydrothionaphthene : Equimolecular proportion of iodothioindoxyl and benzaldehyde (or other components) in absolute ethanol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (2–3 ml.) were refluxed for 10 mins. The iodothioindogenides, thus separated, were recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. The colour of the compounds in H₂SO₄ (Conc.), dyeing shade on cotton from hydrosulphite vat and m.p., crystalline shape, yield, molecular formula and analysis are recorded in Table 2 and 3 respectively.

TABLE 2

T' -- 3 Oxy 2,3-dihydrothionaphthene

Compounds	Colour in Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Shade on cotton
N ₁ : Benzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Blood red	Faint yellow
N ₂ : 2'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Brownish red	Very faint yellow
N ₃ : 3'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Brownish red	Light lemon yellow
N ₄ : 4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Dark brown	Violet red
N ₅ : 4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Brownish red	Violet red
N ₆ : 4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Brownish red	Reddish violet
N ₇ : 4'-Methoxybenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Rose red	Light lemon yellow
N ₈ : 2'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Scarlet red	Brown
N ₉ : 3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Rose red	Reddish violet
N ₁₀ : Cinnamylidene-2-(4-iodo)T	Brownish violet	Light brown
N ₁₁ : 4'-Methoxybenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	Scarlet red	Light brownish yellow
N ₁₂ : 2'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	Reddish brown	Light brown
N ₁₃ : 3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	Rose red	Light reddish violet
N ₁₄ : Cinnamylidene-2-(6-iodo)T	Violet	Light brown
N ₁₅ : 4'-Methoxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	Dark red	Light yellow
N ₁₆ : 2'-Hydroxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	Red	Pink
N ₁₇ : 3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	Dark red	Reddish violet
N ₁₈ : Cinnamylidene-2-(7-iodo)T	Red	Orange yellow

TABLE 3
D = Iodothioindoxyl

Compound	Reactants	Appearance	Yield g.	M.P. °C	Formula	Analysis	
						%Found	%Reqd.
N ₁	B(0.159 g.) + 4-D(0.414 g.) + EtOH(12 ml.)	Bright yellow, clusters of small wooly needles.	0.27	138-39	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₃ IS	I, 35.01 S, 8.68	I, 34.89 S, 8.79
N ₂	<i>o</i> -Nitro B(0.151 g.) + 4-D(0.276 g.) + EtOH (14 ml.)	Yellow, a bundle of fine needles	0.24	174-75	C ₁₅ H ₆ O ₃ NIS	I, 31.00 S, 7.94	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
N ₃	<i>m</i> -Nitro B(0.226 g.) + 4-D(0.414 g.) + EtOH (14 ml.)	Bright yellow, star shaped crystals	0.5	228-29	C ₁₅ H ₆ O ₃ NIS	I, 31.20 S, 7.95	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
N ₄	<i>p</i> -Nitro B(0.226 g.) + 4-D(0.414 g.) + EtOH (18 ml.)	Yellow, a bundle of long fine needles	0.55	229 (Shrinking at 227)	C ₁₅ H ₆ O ₃ NIS	I, 31.15 S, 7.92	I, 31.05 S, 7.82
N ₅	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino B(0.318 g.) + 4-D(0.575 g.) + EtOH (15 ml.)	Maroon, small cylindrical crystals	0.55	207-08	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ONIS	I, 31.00 S, 7.91	I, 31.20 S, 7.86
N ₆	<i>p</i> -Diethylamino B(0.265 g.) + 4-D(0.414 g.) + EtOH (12 ml.)	Dark red, small cylindrical crystals	0.36	155-56	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONIS	I, 29.25 S, 7.52	I, 29.19 S, 7.35
N ₇	4-Methoxy B(0.17 g.) + 4-D(0.345 g.) + EtOH (10 ml.)	Pleasant yellow, foliated needles	0.37	161-62	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ IS	I, 32.37 S, 7.95	I, 32.23 S, 8.12
N ₈	2-Hydroxy B(0.150 g.) + 4-D(0.435 g.) + EtOH (15 ml.)	Brownish red, granular crystals	0.21	209-10	C ₁₅ H ₆ O ₂ IS	I, 33.21 S, 8.49	I, 33.42 S, 8.42
N ₉	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy B(0.169 g.) + 4-D(0.306 g.) + EtOH (10 ml.)	Brown, small pointed needles	0.37	134-35	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ IS	I, 30.42 S, 8.12	I, 30.97 S, 8.21

B = Benzaldehyde

TABLE 3—(Contd.)
D = Iodothioindoxyl

Compound	Reactants	Appearance	Yield g.	M.P. °C	Formula	Analysis	
						%Found	%Reqd.
N ₁₀	Benzaldehyde (0.198 g.) + 4-D (0.414 g.) + EtOH (10 ml.)	Brown, granular crystals	0.35	97-98	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₃ IS	I, 32.50 S, 7.91	I, 32.56 S, 8.20
N ₁₁	Benzaldehyde (0.204 g.) + 6-D (0.414 g.) + EtOH (15 ml.)	Yellow, bundles of long foliated needles.	0.44	183	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ IS	I, 32.29 S, 8.21	I, 32.23 S, 8.12
N ₁₂	2-Hydroxy B (0.15 g.) + 6-D (0.345 g.) + EtOH (10 ml.)	Orange red, stout cylindrical with branches.	0.2	230-31	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ IS	I, 33.51 S, 8.49	I, 33.42 S, 8.42
N ₁₃	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy B (0.169 g.) + 6-D (0.306 g.) + EtOH (10 ml.)	Orange yellow, wooly needles	0.35	139-40	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ IS	I, 31.31 S, 7.98	I, 30.97 S, 7.80
N ₁₄	Cinnamaldehyde (0.198 g.) + 6-D (0.414 g.) + EtOH (8 ml.)	Brownish yellow, small granular crystals.	0.41	179-80	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₃ IS	I, 32.48 S, 8.14	I, 32.56 S, 8.20
N ₁₅	4-Methoxy B (0.17 g.) + 7-D (0.345 g.) + EtOH (10 ml.)	Brownish yellow, bundles of long stout needles.	0.37	191	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ IS	I, 32.30 S, 8.25	I, 32.23 S, 8.12
N ₁₆	2-Hydroxy B (0.15 g.) + 7-D (0.345 g.) + EtOH (15 ml.)	Brown, stout needles	0.18	219-20	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ IS	I, 33.56 S, 8.51	I, 33.42 S, 8.42
N ₁₇	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy B (0.169 g.) + 7-D (0.306 g.) + EtOH (10 ml.)	Reddish brown, small granular crystals.	0.35	178-79	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ IS	I, 31.10 S, 8.00	I, 30.97 S, 7.80
N ₁₈	Cinnamaldehyde (0.198 g.) + 7-D (0.414 g.) + EtOH (10 ml.)	Orange red, small granular crystals	0.44	144-45 (Shrinking at 120)	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₃ IS	I, 32.62 S, 7.98	I, 32.56 S, 8.20

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